

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

**Assoc. Prof Adekunle
Olusola OTUNLA**

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

**Dr Michael
GBADEGESIN**

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

**Dr Emmanuel O.
MALOMO**

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

**Rebecca Oluwatosin
BANJO**

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

**Dr Emmanuel Selome
FASINU**

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

© 2026 Authors

**Yorùbá Philosophy on Transmigration
(*Àkúdááyà*) in the Light of Lazarus'
Resuscitation in John 11:38-44 and
12:1-2**

Boluwatife David OLUGBEMIGA

*Department of Christian Theology, Christ
Apostolic Church Theological Seminary, Ile-Ife,
Osun State, Nigeria*

(An Affiliate of Joseph Ayo Babalola University)

+2348133878318, boluwatifeacadada@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-1726-7333>

Joshua Oluwasegun OLUWASANJO

*Christ Apostolic Church Theological Seminary, Ile-
Ife, Osun State, Nigeria*

(An Affiliate of Joseph Ayo Babalola University)

+2348137205864, jossydonald02@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4846-6937>

Abstract

The doctrine of the afterlife is common to both Yorùbá and Christian religions, and the transmigration (*àkúdááyà*) narrative among the Yorùbá takes a prominent place. Previous studies have dealt with its relationship with unfulfilled destiny and untimely death. This paper aims to establish the notion that the transmigration (*àkúdááyà*) narrative is non-Christian and non-biblical, and that resuscitation is what the Bible teaches. Using historico-grammatical hermeneutics of John 11:38-44 and 12:1-2, this paper found that there are more differences between the theological and philosophical understandings of the two religions bordering on nature and identity of posthumous existence, case of untimely death, relationship with the former environment, and empirical evidence of posthumous life. The paper concludes that the transmigration (*àkúdááyà*)

narrative is non-Christian and non-biblical and should not be embraced by Yorùbá Christians and believers elsewhere. The paper recommends cultural sensitivity, dialogue, and a biblically-oriented worldview for Yorùbá Christians.

Keywords: Transmigration (*Àkúdàáyà*); Resuscitation; Afterlife; Yorùbá Religion; Christian Theology;

Introduction

The concept of life after death has long been a fascinating subject across cultures and religious traditions. In Yorùbá philosophy, the belief in transmigration, a phenomenon where an individual, presumed dead, is believed to continue living elsewhere under a different identity, offers a unique perspective on the afterlife. This view aligns with the Yorùbá understanding of death as a transition rather than a definitive end. In contrast, Christianity presents the resuscitation, particularly the case of Lazarus (Jn. 11:1-44; 12:1-2), as a miraculous return to life in the same form and environment, representing God's power over death. Oftentimes, resuscitation is the appropriate description of those who came back to life aside Jesus, for some reasons to be established in this paper.

Previous studies by Rzeźniczek et al (2023) already scrutinised Lazarus' narrative from the medical perspective, describing the incidence as "Autoresuscitation," "Lazarus Phenomenon," and "Lazarus Syndrome" (pp. 4704). From a medical standpoint, possible causes of Lazarus Syndrome were suggested to be hyperventilation and alkalosis, auto-PEEP (Positive End Expiratory Pressure), delayed drug action, hypothermia, intoxication, metabolic disorders (hyperkalemia), and unobserved minimal vital signs. Some of the incidences of Lazarus Syndrome recorded have lasted not longer than 90 minutes, and not shorter than 6 minutes. It was also reported that the youngest patient was 9 months old, and the oldest was 97 years old. However, this paper will address the case from a biblical standpoint.

This paper aims to explore Yorùbá philosophy on transmigration in light of the resuscitation of Lazarus, providing a comparative analysis of these two distinct interpretations of life after death. By examining the spiritual and cultural nuances of both, the paper seeks to uncover commonalities and differences, particularly in how death is understood and what comes after.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to bridge African traditional beliefs and Christian theology, contributing to the broader discourses on life, death, and the afterlife. As the African religious landscape

increasingly engages with Christianity, it becomes crucial to understand how traditional beliefs, such as transmigration, coexist and interact with Christian doctrines like resuscitation. Scholars such as Olupona (2011) emphasise how this belief shapes the Yorùbá worldview and their understanding of existence. Oripeloye & Omigbule (2019) explore that death often does not come as an experience in homogeneity, but in different manifestations. Olaleye & Okedokun (2022) further note that the profound meaning of death in Yorùbá cosmology, noting the complex relationship between the physical and spiritual worlds, death is a transition, according to an individual's predestination.

The scope of this paper focuses on the Yorùbá belief in transmigration and the Christian concept of resuscitation, using Lazarus' resuscitation as a key case study. This paper shall not be bothered about the broad concept of life after death experience in Yorùbá religion: reincarnation (*àtúnwáyé*), transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) and born to die (*àbíku*); but shall limit its discussions to transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*). The study will examine the theological, philosophical, and cultural dimensions of these two perspectives, offering insights into how different traditions interpret the boundaries among life, death, and the afterlife.

Yorùbá Philosophy on Transmigration (*Àkúdàáyà*)

This section shall delve into the concept, role, implications, and contemporary criticism of transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*). The Yorùbá concept called *àkúdàáyà* is derived from a phrase that literally translates as "one who dies and yet wakes up in another place," which Adegbamigbe (2022) also called "transmigrated soul" (pp. 51). This etymology reflects the core of the belief system surrounding transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) in Yorùbá cosmology, which posits that certain individuals, though declared dead, continue their existence in a different, often far-off place with a new identity (Akomolafe, 2016). This belief is deeply embedded in Yorùbá metaphysics, where life is not seen as terminating with death but as entering another phase of existence. In this belief, transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) represents a unique interpretation of death that transcends finality, allowing for a physical continuation of life.

In addition, Osanyinbi & Falana (2016) opine that the belief in transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) is tied to the broader Yorùbá worldview, which recognises the coexistence of both the physical and spiritual realms. In

Yorùbá thought, a person consists of both a physical body and a spiritual essence - what is commonly known as *èmí* (soul or life force) and *orí* (destiny or spiritual self). The destiny (*orí*), which is divinely assigned, plays a central role in determining a person's fate, and this belief extends to the possibility that after physical death, a person may continue to exist in another location as a transmigrated soul (*àkúdàáyà*). This metaphysical outlook challenges the finality of death, proposing instead that life persists in varied forms.

Again, reports of encounters with transmigrated souls (*àkúdàáyà*) are often surrounded by mystique and treated with a sense of reverence. Such individuals are said to relocate to distant lands, where they take on new identities, with the similitude of the buried bodies, and live normal lives, completely detached from their original and previous communities. The belief offers an explanation for the inexplicable: where people believed to have passed away reappear or are encountered by people in other regions (Fatokun & Hofmyer, 2008).

The roles of transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) in Yorùbá cosmology disclose that death is viewed as part of a continuum of existence. It is not seen as an end, but as a passage from one realm of being to another. This understanding is reflected in the Yorùbá practices of ancestor veneration, and the belief in reincarnation (*àtúnwáyé*), and transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) narrations. Reincarnation (*àtúnwáyé*) is such that the ancestor returns, reborn to the same family, in a new body; while transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) implies a continuation of life in the same physical form, albeit in a new historical context. This belief is thus situated within the broader Yorùbá spiritual understanding that life is cyclical, and death merely marks a transition (Fatokun & Hofmyer, 2008).

Similarly, the phenomenon of transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) also highlights the Yorùbá understanding of the fluidity between the physical and spiritual worlds. In Yorùbá belief, the spiritual and physical are closely linked, and it is not uncommon for individuals to move between these realms in different ways. Transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) is one such movement, where the person's essence does not transition to the spiritual realm fully but instead remains tethered to the physical world in a new and different capacity. This fluidity is germane to understanding the phenomenon within the larger metaphysical framework of the Yorùbá worldview (Osanyinbi & Falana, (2016).

As to the social and cultural implications of transmigration (*àkúdááyà*), the beliefs and narratives provide a coping mechanism and closure for family members and neighbours in the event of sudden or unexplainable death. Families and communities may take comfort in the idea that their loved one continues to live, even if they are no longer part of their immediate environment. This belief offers a form of spiritual reassurance that death is not the end of the individual's journey.

In the same vein, the concept of transmigration (*àkúdááyà*) often serves a cultural function, providing narratives that help explain the mysteries of death and reward or completion of a short-lived life, even while it is mythical and non-empirical (Adegbamigbe, 2022). For instance, the Yorùbá community believes that not all deaths are natural; some are caused by awful incidents, spiritual forces or unresolved destinies and result in the untimely exit from the physical world, leaving no offerings behind, and an unceremonious burial (Akomolafe, 2016). As O'láléyè & Òkédòkun (2022) note, Yorùbá traditional religion emphasises the dynamic and interconnected nature of life and death. The idea of transmigrated souls provides further depth to this, allowing for an ongoing interaction between the two realms.

While the phenomenon of transmigration (*àkúdááyà*) has spiritual and emotional implications, it equally highlights the importance of communal memory and social identity in Yorùbá culture. An individual's existence extends beyond the physical, as long as they are remembered or encountered in some form. The belief in transmigration (*àkúdááyà*) emphasises the Yorùbá conviction that identity is fluid, and individuals are defined not only by their life in one place but by their potential to continue existing elsewhere (Olufadekemi, 2019). However, the lack of empirical data on the narrative does not make it an acceptable religious belief to the scientific man. While it remains a significant part of Yorùbá religious and cultural identity, because it aids the understanding of the relationship between the visible and invisible worlds, it is unverifiable (O'láléyè & Òkédòkun, 2022).

Can a Christian Corpse Become a Wraith?

The question of whether a Christian corpse can become a wraith (a ghost wandering about), particularly within the context of Yorùbá philosophy of transmigration, raises significant theological and doctrinal issues. The concept of transmigration is incompatible with Christian teachings on

death, the body, and the afterlife. From a Christian worldview, it is clear that a Christian corpse cannot become a wraith, and this position is firmly grounded in both Scripture and Christian doctrine. The evidence is based on the Scriptural perspectives on death, resuscitation, and Christian doctrine on the integrity of the body. The subject of resurrection will also be discussed because of the blurred perspectives between resurrection and resuscitation.

Scriptural perspectives on death uphold the view that death marks the end of a person's earthly existence and the beginning of eternal life, either in communion with God or in separation from Him. From Hebrews 9:27, "It is appointed for men to die once, but after this the judgment," Christian belief is that after death, there is no possibility of returning to life in another/similar form, as the person's fate is sealed for eternity, even as his works follow him (cf. 1 Tim. 5:24-25). From 1 Thessalonians 4:15-17, believers who are dead, described as "asleep in the Lord," will rise on the day of the first resurrection, which is the same day as the rapture of the living believers and thus, deceased believers will not rise earlier than that day. From John 11:24, the Jews believe that resurrection of the dead is on the Last Day, not prior, and that is one reason to rethink Lazarus, Jairus' daughter and the widow of Nain's son's resurrection as strictly *resuscitation of life*. Even so, resurrection is with a glorious physical body, unto an eternal abode, but those characters came back with the same old bodies, to their former neighbourhood and died again, awaiting resurrection. The concept of transmigration contradicts this fundamental teaching.

Similarly, the resurrection of the body, as exemplified in the resurrection of Jesus Christ (1 Cor. 15:20-22), provides a clear and definitive answer to the question of life after death. In Christian teaching, resurrection is a transformation into an eternal, glorified state, not a mere continuation of earthly life under a different identity, seen as a phantom. The body that dies is not up for use after death, as the believer's ultimate hope lies in the resurrection of the dead on the final day (1 Thess. 4:13-18).

Furthermore, none of the Bible characters had his or her body used as a wraith, not even Elijah, believed to have returned as John the Baptist (Mal. 4:5-6; cf. Lk. 1:16-17; Jn. 1:19-21). John the Baptist was not Elijah, but had the same ministry as him, described as "in the spirit and power of Elijah." Moses and Elijah's appearance in Matthew 17:1-3 is not the appearance of their apparitions/wraith, but a vision for the disciples who could grasp the

revelation of the glorified Messiah (v. 9) as the Law and Prophets hand over their baton (Constable, 2023). They did not appear as real humans after their death, but in a vision; thus, they are not transmigrated souls. Transmigrated souls can be seen by both initiates and novices of the traditional religion, but the disciples who saw Moses and Elijah saw them in a vision. Elijah and Moses, like all other Old Testament saints, will resurrect on the Last Day (cf. Heb. 11:39-40).

Christian doctrine on the integrity of the body is rooted in the fact that the believer's body is the temple of the Holy Spirit (1 Cor. 6:19-20), and as such cannot be subjected to manipulation by magical or wizardry means. This understanding reinforces the sanctity of the body, even in death. The body of a Christian is treated with respect and dignity because of the belief in the eventual resurrection of the body. The idea that a Christian corpse could become a wraith - essentially reanimated in another/similar form - undermines this belief in the sanctity of the body and projects that the body can be possessed when actually the Holy Spirit dwells therein. This notion would be logically incompatible with 1 Corinthians 6:19-20 and Ephesians 1:13-14. The integrity of the body in Christian thought means that it cannot be manipulated or reanimated for purposes other than what God has ordained (Tasmuth, 2020).

Additionally, Romans 6:8-9 and 1 Corinthians 15:53-54 speak to the finality of death for Christians, in that just as Christ's body could not be held down by death, so will the believers'. The Christian belief is that after death, the soul departs to be with the Lord, and the body awaits the resurrection. Again, Jesus' discussion on the state of the body at death and resurrection is that marriage and gender will be erased, and believers will be in angelic forms (Matt. 22:23-33; Lk. 20:34-35) (Plumpton, 2012). This denotes that the body of the Christian corpse cannot be termed male or female, nor can it get entangled in a romantic relationship, let alone sire children, because it is now in an angelic form. This is unlike transmigration narrations in Yorùbá land, where such a corpse sires children and gets married in a different historical context. This is another reason to perceive Lazarus, Jairus' daughter and the widow of Nain's son's resurrection as strictly *resuscitation of life*. Therefore, the body cannot serve as a vessel for further earthly existence, as believed in the Yorùbá notion of transmigration.

Corroborating this notion are Augustine of Hippo and Thomas Aquinas. Augustine (2003), in his treatise on *The City of God*, affirms the finality of

death for Christians, asserting that the body and soul are temporarily separated at death until the final resurrection. This separation precludes the possibility of the body being reanimated in a wraith-like state, as there is no Scriptural or theological basis for such an occurrence in Christian eschatology. Furthermore, Aquinas (1981) in his *Summa Theologica* argues that the soul, once departed from the body at death, cannot return to animate the body until the resurrection at the end of time. This assertion aligns with the biblical teaching that the dead are either in the presence of God or in a state of separation from Him, awaiting final judgment. Therefore, the Yorùbá belief in transmigration stands in stark contrast to this Christian teaching, as it suggests that a person can resume life in a similar form but in a different location after death. Such a belief is inconsistent with the Christian understanding of death, the resurrection of the body, and the eternal fate of the soul.

Theologically, the idea of a Christian corpse being a wraith conflicts with the hope of the resurrection and the victory over death won by Christ (1 Cor. 15:55-57). In Christian theology, death is not something to be feared or manipulated but rather a defeated enemy through the work of Christ. To entertain the possibility that a Christian body could become a wraith would undermine the foundational Christian doctrine of resurrection and the finality of Christ's victory over death. In addition, Christian eschatology emphasises the integrity and purpose of the body in both life and death. A belief that a Christian body could be reanimated or used in a wraith-like state would contradict the respect and dignity accorded to the body as part of God's creation, destined for eternal glory.

Hermeneutics of John 11:38-44 and 12:1-2

Now, it is important to establish that Lazarus was resuscitated and not resurrected by presenting biblical proofs from the passage of the event. According to Edwards (2015), the Gospel of John (εὐαγγέλιον κατὰ Ἰωάννην; *euangelion kata Joannê*) is the fourth of the four canonical gospels, with a set out purpose, "that you may believe that Jesus is the Christ, the Son of God, and that believing you may have life in his name" (pp. 171). One of such events that provides evidence for belief is the resuscitation of Lazarus. It was Jesus' way of presenting himself as the "the Resurrection and the Life," after he had earlier given evidences of being the Bread of Life (6:35, 41, 48, 51), the Light of the World (8:12; 9:5), the Door of the Sheep (10:7,

9), and the Good Shepherd (10:11, 14). This fifth sign comes at the time of Jesus' fifth absolute "I AM", and was later followed by the sixth and seventh "I AMs" of the Way, Truth, and Life (14:6), and the True Vine (15:1, 5), respectively. For Akpa, Nwaomah, & Umahi (2013), this event was the most powerful revelation of His true identity, as He exercised authority over death, man's last enemy to be destroyed (cf. 5:21, 25, and 28). For Carson & Moo (2005), this event also foreshadowed His imminent Resurrection. Definitely, Jesus' testimonies are backed up by signs, evident to all. Verse 38 details Jesus' "agony, trouble, agitation" (ἐμβριμώμενος: *embrimômenos*) occasioned by Jewish unbelief (v. 37) as he approached the tomb of Lazarus. For Constable, that tomb was cut into the limestone hillsides, common at that time, as the site for "tombs" (μνημεῖον: *mnêmeion*). Normally, a large round stone sealed the entrance against animals and curious individuals. But this stone would soon be removed by the same people who enclosed Lazarus. This is evident in verse 39 as Jesus commanded that the large stone be removed. Martha, Lazarus's sister, who thought that the resurrection of her brother by Jesus would be at a later time in the end of times, demonstrated her unbelief again (cf. vv. 23-24) by saying that the corpse would be "stinking" (ἤδη ὀζει: *édê ozei*), because it had been laid "there for four days" (τεταρταῖος γὰρ ἔστιν: *tetartaios gar estin*). Somewhat, none of the Jews, standing by, and Jesus himself bothered themselves with the ceremonial law requiring that no one should touch a corpse (cf. Lev. 11:24-47), and some ritual cleansing that would be required, in any eventuality. According to Sanders (1968), this may be because the Jews customarily wrapped the bodies of their dead in cloth, and they added spices to counteract the odours that decomposition produced. They did not embalm them as thoroughly as the Egyptians did. Perhaps they had learned that ritual uncleanness was not something that bothered Jesus, even as his sacrifice would later be the culmination of all the sacrifices (Lev. 11:24-47). In verses 40-41, Jesus replies to Martha in the same way He did in verses 25-26, and the people "rolled away the stone" (ἤρραν οὖν τὸν λίθον: *êpav oun ton lithon*) at Martha's plea with them. It might have been a plea because the Jews would have wondered what Jesus was about to do, and maybe he would trespass on Mosaic Law regarding contact with the dead. This would have been an opportunity to nail him. While everyone was staring at Him, "He lifted up his eyes" (ὁ δὲ Ἰησοῦς ἤρην τοὺς ὀφθαλμοὺς ἀνω: *o de jêsus êren tous ophthalmous anô*) to heaven and gave thanks to the Father (Πάτερ,

εὐχαριστῶ σοι ὅτι ἤκουσός μου: *Pater, eucharistô soi oti êkousas mou*), to show that the miracle He was about to perform was already decreed by the Father (cf. v. 11), that it would be an evidence that He is the Resurrection and the Life (v. 42), and that He was not a necromancer nor a magician (Trench, 1915).

Verses 43-44 culminate the passage with Jesus specifically “calling forth Lazarus” (Ἀόζαρε, δεῦρο ἐξῶ!: *Lazare, deuro exô!*) so that not every corpse was being addressed. Lazarus, being Jesus’ own, heard His voice and responded (5:25, 28-29; 10:3). Jesus also spoke loudly, unlike wizards and magicians who mutter their incantations and spells quietly (cf. Isa. 8:19). Everyone heard Jesus and knew that nothing shady was happening, as is typical of magicians and necromancers. The first miracle was that the dead heard Him, showing that He was only κεκοιμηται (*kekoimêtai*: asleep) (cf. 11:11), just like every deceased believer in Christ is and will be. The second miracle is that, despite having his hands and feet bound with burial garments, he could not be restrained but δεῦρο ἐξῶ (*deuro exô*: came forth). Lazarus’ transmigration is strictly described as ἐξῆλθεν (*ezêlthen*: came out of/resuscitated from) the dead, not as resurrection (ἀνάστασις: *anastasis*), because believers will resurrect with a glorious body free of sin (cf. 20:19, 26; 1 Cor. 15:35-49), live with Jesus eternally, and never die again, as depicted in Jesus’ resurrection. However, Lazarus “came out of the dead” (ἐξῆλθεν ὁ τεθνηκώς: *ezêlthen o tethnêkôs*), out of the tomb with the same physical body, returning to his neighbourhood, still prone to sin, and died again. Additionally, from John 11:24, the Jews believe that the resurrection of the dead occurs on the Last Day, not before (Jn. 5:28-29; 1 Cor. 15:42, 50; 1 Thess. 4:13-18; Rev. 20:5; cf. Jb. 19:25-27; Ps. 49:13-15; Isa. 26:19; Dan. 12:1-2). Furthermore, Lazarus did not become like angels when he came out of the tomb, as Jesus earlier taught (cf. Matt. 22:30). Thus, it was not only Lazarus who was resuscitated by God’s miraculous power, but also Jairus’ daughter (Mk. 5:41-42), the widow of Nain’s son (Lk. 7:14-15), Dorcas (Acts 9:36-41), and Eutychus (Acts 20:9-11).

Quite amazing is that Lazarus, whom Jesus had physically “raised/resuscitated” (ἠγείρεν: *égeistren*) from the dead, was physically alive to attend the dinner in honour of Jesus, six days before Passover at Bethany (12:1). He was reclining, enjoying the “meals” (δειπνον: *deipnon*), was an empirical proof to the people of Bethany, his hometown where he lived with his family (11:1) before his initial death. When he came back to live, he lived

in the same family house and neighbourhood. He was empirically proven by the five sensory perceptions of his neighbours, family and the Jewish community (12:9) to be alive. While the word used is ἰδῶσιν (*idôsîn*: that they might see), it depicts *understanding* (cf. Mk. 4:12), which is obtained by empiricism and not assumption. This miracle is uncommon to many wraiths in African societies, as what is common to them is manipulation by magical means to live again, and so they do not and cannot bear witnesses to their afterlife existence on earth again. They literally move to distant lands to continue their lives, disappear once they contact any known relatives, and are phantoms, rather than real (Akomolafe, 2016).

Comparative Analysis of Transmigration (*Àkúdááyà*) and Resurrection/Resuscitation

The concept of transmigration (*àkúdááyà*) in Yorùbá philosophy and the Christian doctrine of resuscitation/resurrection represent two distinct interpretations of life after death. Both views grapple with the mystery of death and posthumous existence, but their fundamental standpoints about life, death, and the afterlife differ significantly. While there are areas of potential intersection, the divergences are more pronounced, particularly in terms of the purpose, nature, and theological implications of these phenomena. The areas of intersection of Yorùbá philosophy on transmigration and Christian doctrine of resurrection/resuscitation are basically in the possibility and reality of posthumous existence of man, and the continuation of identity in the afterlife. This section shall juxtapose the three ideas for more clarity.

On posthumous existence, both transmigration and resurrection involve the continuation of existence after death. Transmigrated souls, despite being dead to their former communities, are believed to be living elsewhere, as the same human beings they were, often with a new identity. Similarly, in Christianity, resurrection embodies the idea that life continues after death, albeit in a glorified, sinless and eternal form, as exemplified by the resurrection of Jesus Christ and would be for all believers (*Ticciati, 2023*). For Lazarus, he was not a wraith, a ghost, nor an apparition of himself, but his real identity was maintained in the former community, both in death and in resuscitation. Lazarus was alive on the other end and could therefore respond to Jesus' call, just as transmigrated souls relate with their

environment. These notions suggest a strong belief in the persistence of life beyond physical death.

In addition, Ọlálẹyẹ & Ọkédòkun (2022) assert that human personal identity is beyond physical death. In transmigration, the individual maintains his personality and essence, such as names, gender, and social roles, and so is recognized by former relatives; he only changes location. Similarly, in Christian resurrection/resuscitation, like that of Lazarus, the individual is raised to new life with the same human personality and essence of names, gender and social or religious status, but with a transformed body that sin cannot overcome, in resurrection. However, while the individual in resurrection is seen as glorified (sinless, unbound by natural laws), transmigrated souls continue to exist as phantoms to their former neighbourhood, often leading a normal life in a new community.

The areas of divergence between the two doctrines are the nature of posthumous existence, the issue of untimely death, the relationship with the former environment, and empirical evidence of posthumous life. On the nature of posthumous existence, the Yorùbá believe in transmigrated souls, who wander as ghosts, roam until they find rest and complete their lives' cycles. Such individuals are said to move to different, often distant locations after death and continue to live a relatively ordinary life in human form, albeit under a different identity. The Yorùbá cosmology suggests that the soul of an individual who met untimely death can return as a transmigrated soul, often necessitated by spiritual forces or unresolved destiny (Osadola, 2022). By contrast, Christian resurrection is not merely a continuation of life but a complete transformation of existence. Christians believe in the resurrection as a supernatural event in which the dead are raised to eternal life in communion with God or in eternal separation from Him. The resurrected body is glorified, incorruptible, and eternal (1 Cor. 15:42-44). The Christian doctrine does not allow for the idea that dead individuals continue life in their former or new communities under different/similar identities. Instead, whenever resuscitation occurs, the raised individual continues life in his former community with the former identity as a witness to what God has truly done, like in the case of Lazarus. In heaven, at the final resurrection, transformed identity in a new heavenly community is achieved (Ticciati, 2023).

Another major divergence is the concept of untimely death. According to Falola (2010), Yorùbá religion believed that certain deaths are "premature

or untimely,” referred to as *ikú ait’òjò*. Such deaths are often considered the result of unresolved destinies, awful death, or spiritual forces, and in most cases, the individual returns as a transmigrated soul to continue life elsewhere. The belief is that the person has unfinished business and therefore their spirit, or essence, continues in another form (pp. 57). However, Christian theology teaches that death is a part of God’s divine plan and that there is no such thing as “untimely death” because man’s cycle of days is divinely ordained (Job 7:9-10; 14:5, 12; 16:22; Ps. 78:39; 139:16; Heb. 9:27). Also, the righteous lives a longer life while the wicked suffers untimely death (Pro. 10:27, 30). However, in the case of arguing that untimely death could be a Christian experience, the prodding question becomes: who keeps the divine time as to ascertain that Ananias, Saphira, John the Baptist, James and Stephen died untimely? The understanding that man’s cycle of days is divinely ordained certainly explains that death would make an excuse, such as sin and sickness. It is significant to equally understand that there is a reduction in life expectancy since the fall of Man (Gen. 6:3; Ps. 90:10). Lazarus died “untimely,” not because he was wicked, but so that the disciples might believe that Jesus owns the key to life and death (Jn. 11:14-15, 25-26). For Kim (2011) Lazarus’ resuscitation and longer years on earth underscored God’s promise, and peradventure that did not happen on earth, it will happen in heaven. Therefore, Augustine (2003) accentuates the Christians believe that death happens according to God’s perfect will and timing, believers do not experience the finality of death, and there is no return to earthly life after death, except through the final resurrection.

Furthermore, the difference lies in the relationship between the deceased and their former environment. In the belief surrounding transmigration, it is understood that the soul does not settle in their former community. They must relocate and start a new life elsewhere, adopting a new identity. This relocation is necessary to maintain the mystery and distance from their former life. The transmigrated soul is effectively severed from their previous identity and connections. Conversely, in Christian resurrection, there is no notion of moving to a new environment or taking a new identity. In fact, after Jesus’ resurrection, He returned to His disciples and appeared to them multiple times in His glorified body, affirming His identity and continuity with His earthly life (Lk. 24:36-43; Jn. 20:19-29), same as Lazarus who continued living with his family and relatives’ post-resuscitation (Jn. 12:1-

2, 9) and participating in the former religious and social life. Christians believe that in the resurrection, the individual is raised in the same body, fully recognizable by all former acquaintances and relatives, and continues his existence in the presence of God.

Lastly, the empirical nature of posthumous life further distinguishes transmigration from resurrection/resuscitation. In the Yorùbá belief, there is little to no empirical proof that the transmigrated soul maintains a physical presence, only a phantom. The existence of these wraith-like figures is often based on anecdotal evidence and spiritual experiences within the community, making it largely speculative. There are often no verifiable accounts or observable evidence of the individual's continued life, which contributes to the mystical nature of the belief. Most times, a transmigrated soul, when seen, cannot be touched, smelled, or heard by his former relatives, except for strangers who, once they know his identity as a wraith, would disappear from their reach. In contrast, Christianity provides empirical evidence of the resurrection and resuscitation, particularly in the case of Jairus' daughter, the widow of Nain's son, Lazarus and Jesus Christ. The resurrection of Jesus was witnessed by His disciples and many others, providing a historical and empirical foundation for the belief in resurrection (1 Cor. 15:3-8). According to Wright (2003), the physical resurrection of Jesus is central to the Christian faith, and His appearances to His followers are presented as verifiable proofs of the reality of resurrection. Lazarus resuscitation was proven by his community members who came to ἰδῶσιν (*idōsin*: see, behold, understand, perceive, attend to, experience) him, and this underscores that the historical event was a divine, real, verifiable, reliable, and empirical event.

Conclusion

Transmigration (*àkúdáàáyà*) is a non-Christian and non-biblical concept rooted in African philosophy of life after death. It differs in many ways from biblical doctrines on death, resurrection/resuscitation, and Christian doctrine on the integrity of the body. Wraith-like existence is in different historical and philosophical contexts, particularly following an argument on untimely death. The Christian resurrection is a divine, transformative event leading to eternal life with God, transcending earthly existence, and in cases of references to resuscitation, such existence on earth is not mystical, mythical or distant, but divine, real, verifiable, reliable, replicable and

empirical. Thus, Yorùbá Christians should not buy into the narratives of transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) as popularised by African philosophy, because they are non-Christian and non-biblical concepts.

Recommendations

The paper recommends that Christian missionaries should approach transmigration (*àkúdàáyà*) narratives with cultural sensitivity while clearly distinguishing them from Christian resuscitation/resurrection. Similarly, promoting dialogue between adherents of both faiths can foster deeper understanding and clarify doctrinal differences. Lastly, Yorùbá Christians' orientation of life and death should be sourced from the Bible, while they also avoid presumptuous hermeneutics of given passages, so that cultural heritage and theological clarity can be achieved.

References

- Adegbamigbe, A. A. (2022). The mystery of *Akudaaya* in Yoruba films: Interrogating death and destiny in *Aye Loja*, directed by Seun Olaiya. *Scholars: Journal of Arts & Humanities*, 4(2), 51.
- Akomolafe, M. A. (2016). Yoruba ontology: A critique of the conceptualisation of life after death. *Africology: The Journal of Pan African Studies*, 9(6), 43–45.
- Akpa, M., Nwaomah, S., & Umahi, G. (2013). Death and resurrection in John 11: Implications for Seventh-day Adventist mission in Africa. *Journal of Adventist Mission Studies*, 9(2), 140–141.
- Aquinas, T. (1981). *Summa theologica* (Vol. I–II, Q. 75). Christian Classics. (Original work published ca. 1265–1274)
- Augustine of Hippo. (2003). *The city of God*. Penguin Books.
- Carson, D. A., & Moo, D. J. (2005). *An introduction to the New Testament* (2nd ed.). Zondervan.
- Constable, T. L. (2023). *Notes on John*. Sonic Light.
- Edwards, R. B. (2015). *Discovering John: Content, interpretation, reception*. William B. Eerdmans.
- Falola, T. (2010). *Yorùbá culture: A philosophical analysis*. Carolina Academic Press.
- Fatokun, S., & Hofmeyr, H. (2008). African Christians' attitude to African traditional belief in rebirth (reincarnation): A critique. *Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae*, 34, 457–474.
- Kim, S. S. (2011). The significance of Jesus' raising Lazarus from the dead in John 11. *Bibliotheca Sacra*, 168(669), 62.

- Oláláyé, S. K., & Òkédòkun, A. (2022). The concept of death in Yorùbá indigenous belief as depicted by Ifá divination system in Oyékú-Pòsé. *African Journal of Religion, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(1), 111–128.
- Olufadekemi, A. (2019). The reality and non-peculiarity of the Yorùbá's belief in reincarnation: *Aye keji* exemplified. *International Review of Humanities Studies*, 4(2), Article 10, 667.
- Olupona, J. K. (2011). *City of 201 gods: Ile-Ife in time, space, and the imagination*. University of California Press.
- Oripeloye, H., & Omigbule, M. B. (2019). The Yoruba of Nigeria and the ontology of death and burial. In *Death across cultures: Death and dying in non-Western cultures* (pp. 193–205).
- Osadola, O. S. (2022). Reincarnation in the Yoruba ontology. *Matondang Journal*, 2(1), 27–35.
- Osanyinbi, O. B., & Falana, K. (2016). An evaluation of the Akure Yorùbá traditional belief in reincarnation. *Open Journal of Philosophy*, 6, 59–67.
- Plumptre, E. H. (2012). Matthew 22:30. In C. J. Ellicott (Ed.), *A New Testament commentary for English readers, by various writers* (p. 138). E. P. Dutton & Co.
- Rzeźniček, P., Gaczowska, A. D., Kluzik, A., Cybulski, M., Bartkowska-Śniatkowska, A., & Grzeškowiak, M. (2023). Lazarus phenomenon or the return from the afterlife—What we know about auto resuscitation. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(14), Article 4704. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12144704>
- Sanders, J. N. A. (1968). Commentary on the Gospel according to St. John. In B. A. Mastin (Ed.), *Black's New Testament commentaries series* (p. 274). Adam & Charles Black.
- Tasmuth, R. (2020). Pauline anthropology: Temples and bodies as God's sanctuaries. *Open Access Journal of Archaeology & Anthropology*, 2(4), 1–3.
- Ticciati, S. (2023). Resurrection of the dead. In B. N. Wolfe et al. (Eds.), *St. Andrews encyclopaedia of theology*. <https://www.saet.ac.uk/Christianity/ResurrectionoftheDead>
- Trench, R. C. (1915). *Synonyms of the New Testament*. Kegan Paul, Trench, Trübner & Co.
- Wright, N. T. (2003). *The resurrection of the Son of God*. Fortress Press.